

Extraction studies of Cd^{II} from hydrochloric acid media using Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 extractants. Application to its recovery from spent Ni-Cd battery

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Abstract : The effectiveness of Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 as extractants for cadmium(II) extraction from hydrochloric acid solution is studied as a function of several variables such as acidity, reagent concentration, equilibration time and diluents. Quantitative extraction was found in the range 4.0–7.0 M HCl and 6.0–7.0 M HCl with Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 in toluene respectively. Stripping of metal loaded organic phase of Cyanex-923 was done with 1.0 M HNO₃, however 2.0 M HNO₃ was required for complete stripping of the metal from Cyanex-925 organic phase. The method was extended for recovery of cadmium from spent Ni-Cd battery.

Keywords : Extractions of metal ions, cadmium(II), nickel-recovery, cadmium-recovery.

The most important use of cadmium is in electroplating various metals and alloys to provide a coating that is resistant to corrosion by alkalis, salt water or the atmosphere. Cadmium hydroxide is the anode material of Ag-Cd and Ni-Cd rechargeable storage batteries. CdS, CdSe and CdTe find utility in solar cells. CdS and sulfoselenide are used as colourants for plastics, glass, glazes, rubber and fireworks. CdTe is used in infrared optics, electroluminescent devices, photocells and as a detector for nuclear radiation. Halides of cadmium are used in photography, lithography and process engraving.

Liquid-liquid extraction and separation of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} was carried out by ketone like 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-acyl-5-pyrazolones¹. Extraction of divalent metals like Zn^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} with bis (2,4,4-trimethyl pentyl) phosphinic acid² was also studied. The decreasing order of extraction of the metal ions was found as, Zn^{II} > Cu^{II} > Cd^{II}. The extraction of Cd^{II} from potassium salt solution with 2-thenoyl trifluoroacetone³ was reported. Yoshitaka⁴ studied the extraction of Cd^{II} using a combination of P-t-butyl Calix [8] arene and its derivative and amines. Various organophosphorous acidic extractants⁵ like Cyanex-272, Cyanex-301 and Cyanex-302 are employed for extraction and separation of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}. Synergistic extraction of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} was also performed with carboxylic acid⁶ and bis (5'-hydroxyl-pyrazol-4'-

oyl)alkanes⁷ where by alkane thiols and trioctyl phosphine oxide are added respectively to enhance extraction. Comparative study was carried out using mono (n-octyl) phosphinic and di (n-octyl) phosphinic acid⁸ for the extraction of Cd^{II} and other transition metal ions. The extraction of Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} with di-(2-ethylhexyl)-dithiophosphoric acid (D2EHDTPA) and D2EHDTPA-trioctyl amine in toluene was investigated. It was observed that Cd^{II} was easily extracted by D2EHDTPA however stripping was difficult, this problem was solved when mixture of extractants was employed⁹. N-Benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxyl amine¹⁰ was used for the extraction of Cd^{II}. Recently Rickelton¹¹ studied the extraction of Cd^{II} from the mixture of hydrochloric and phosphoric acid with Cyanex-923 in Exxsol D80.

The extraction of Cd^{II} from potassium oxalate solution by Primene JM-T, Amberlite LA-2, Alamine 336 and Aliquat 336 was studied. It was found that Amberlite LA-2 and Alamine 336 do not extract the metal ion even after the treatment with acids^{12,13}. The extraction of Cd^{II} from iodide solution was investigated by tracer technique with bis-2-ethylhexyl sulfoxide (B2EHSO) in benzene. The nature of the extracted species was CdI₂·2B2EHSO¹⁴. Only 76% of Cd^{II} was extracted from ferrous sulphate solution using diethyldithio carbamate¹⁵ as extractant. Similarly incomplete extraction was shown by 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxyl-5'-

sulformazylbenzene in Tween 80¹⁶. The other extractants which extract Cd^{II} are Acorga M5640¹⁷, 2-thenoyl trifluoroacetone¹⁸, 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-pyrazol-5-one and di-(1-methylheptyl) methyl phosphonate¹⁹. Separation of Cd^{II} using tri-n-octylamine and hexadecylamine as liquid membrane was also carried out effectively^{20,21}. Synergistic extraction of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} was done from sulphate medium by a mixture of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-pyrazol-5-one and methyl isobutyl ketone²². Extraction of cadmium was performed from phosphoric acid using Amberlite XAD-7 resin impregnated with organophosphorous extractant, Cyanex-301²³. Selective separation of Fe^{III}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II} was also carried out from dilute solutions using solvent-impregnated resins like Amberlite XAD-2 with Cyanex-272 and Cyanex-302, extractants²⁴.

In the present work two extractants Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 are used for the extraction of cadmium from hydrochloric acid media. Since cadmium is a typical class "b" ion according to hard soft acid base rule (HSAB), it is expected to be readily extractable with the extracting ligand containing sulphur, oxygen and nitrogen as the donor atoms. As Cyanex-923 possesses "O" as the donor atom extraction of Cd^{II} takes from aqueous phase to organic phase. The method is extended further for the extraction and separation of Cd^{II} from the spent Ni-Cd battery.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents :

The extractants Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 supplied by Cytec Industries Inc. Canada was used without purification. A known amount of CdCl₂ was dissolved in double distilled water and standardized by ammonium phosphate monohydrate method²⁵. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. GBC UV-Visible 911A spectrophotometer with 10 mm cortex cuvettes was used for absorbance measurements.

Procedure :

An aliquot containing 50 µg of Cd^{II} in 10 ml was taken and equilibrated separately with equal volume of Cyanex-923/Cyanex-925 in toluene for the required shaking time of 5 min, after adjusting their aqueous solution to acidity of 4.0 M and 6.0 M HCl respectively. The two phases were allowed to separate. The organic phase containing the metal extracted species from Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 was then stripped quantitatively with 1.0 M and 2.0 M HNO₃ solution respectively and it was determined spectrophotometrically at 575 nm with xylenol orange method²⁶. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature.

Results and discussion

Effect of hydrochloric acid and reagent concentration on the percentage extraction of Cd^{II}.

The effect of HCl concentration on the percentage extraction of Cd^{II} with 0.3 M Cyanex-923/Cyanex-925 in toluene was studied in the acidity range from 1.0–9.0 M. As the acidity increases the extraction goes on increasing and becomes quantitative in the range 4.0–7.0 M HCl and 6.0–7.0 M HCl with Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 in toluene respectively. Hence, all the extractions were carried out at 4.0 M HCl and 6.0 M HCl with Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Effect of hydrochloric acid concentration on percentage extraction of Cd^{II} with Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 in toluene.

Extraction of Cd^{II} was carried out by varying the reagent concentration from 5 × 10⁻² to 3 × 10⁻¹ M in toluene and it was found that the extraction increased with increase in the reagent concentration. The extraction of Cd^{II} was quantitative with 0.3 M Cyanex-923 or Cyanex-925 in toluene.

Table 1. Effect of diverse ions on percentage extraction of Cd^{II} with Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 in toluene

Amount of Cd^{II} = 50 µg, Cyanex-923/Cyanex-925 = 0.3 M, acidity of HCl = 4.0 M/6.0 M, equilibration time = 5 min

Diverse ions	With Cyanex-923,	With Cyanex-925,
	tolerance limit ratio Cd ^{II} : diverse ion	tolerance limit ratio Cd ^{II} : diverse ion
Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , I ⁻ , SO ₃ ²⁻ , citrate, oxalate	1 : 20	1 : 19
Na ^I , K ^I , Cs ^I , Rb ^I	1 : 10	1 : 8
Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , Sr ^{II}		
V ^V , Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	1 : 6	1 : 5
Cr ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , Zn ^{II}	1 : 4	1 : 3
Al ^{III} , Bi ^{III}		
Ru ^{III} , Pt ^{IV} , Pd ^{II} , Au ^{III} , Os ^{VIII} , Rh ^{III}	1 : 0	1 : 0

Fig. 2. Effect of reagent concentration on distribution ratio of cadmium(II).

The extraction of Cd^{II} with Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 was carried using different aliphatic and aromatic diluents like carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, n-hexane, toluene, xylene and cyclohexane. Quantitative extraction with both extractant was observed with all the above diluents except that of chloroform where the percentage extraction is 4.3 and 24.6 respectively. Toluene was preferred as the best diluent for the extraction of Cd^{II} since it provided better phase separation.

Extraction equilibrium was studied for different periods of shaking ranging from 1–20 min. It was observed that 5 min of shaking period was sufficient for quantitative extraction of Cd^{II} with 0.3 M Cyanex-923/Cyanex-925 in toluene. However, there was no adverse effect by increasing the extraction period upto 20 min.

The metal loaded organic phase of Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 was stripped with different strengths of acids like HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄ and HClO₄. The complete recovery of Cd^{II} from metal loaded Cyanex-923 was found with 1.0 M HNO₃ and 3.0 M HClO₄ solution. However 2.0 M HNO₃ and 2.0 M HClO₄ was required for complete stripping from Cyanex-925 organic phase. The other acids showed incomplete recovery of Cd^{II}.

Stoichiometry of the extracted species :

In order to determine the stoichiometry and nature of the extracted species a graph of log *D* versus log *R* was plotted. With increase in the reagent concentration, the distribution ratio goes on increasing. The slopes obtained were 2.05 and 2.00 indicating that two molecules of Cyanex-923/Cyanex-925 react with one molecule of cadmium ion (Fig. 2). Therefore, the stoichiometry of the extracted species is 1 : 2. As Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 are neutral extractants that will extract neutral species from the aqueous phase. The extraction of Cd^{II} is carried out in hydrochloric acid media so the possible extractable species is CdCl₂. Therefore, the probable nature of the extracted species in the organic phase was found to be CdCl₂·2Cyanex-923 and CdCl₂·2Cyanex-925 similar to the earlier reported with trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO)²⁷.

Effect of various diverse ions :

Cd^{II} was extracted with Cyanex-923/Cyanex-925 in the presence of large number of foreign ions. The tolerance limit was set in such a way that the diverse ion causing interference of ±2.0% in the extraction.

It was found that alkali and alkaline metal ions like Na^I, K^I, Cs^I, Rb^I, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II} were highly tolerated in the ratio 1 : 10 and 1 : 8 with Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 respectively (Table 1). However, metal ions Ru^{III}, Pt^{IV}, Pd^{II}, Au^{III}, Os^{VIII}, Rh^{III} interfere strongly during extraction with both the extractants.

Application to the recovery of Cd^{II} from the spent of Ni-Cd battery :

Because of the increasing environmental concern, the disposal of all batteries is reviewed by various workers. In order to reduce or eliminate the scattering of cadmium in the environment, the disposal of Ni-Cd batteries was studied. Recycling programmes have been instituted by several battery manufacturers in France, Belgium, Japan, Sweden and Korea aimed at reducing cadmium pollution from the spent Ni-Cd batteries²⁸. Acidic organophosphorous extractants like Cyanex-301 and Cyanex-302 and neutral extractant like Kelex-100 have been employed for the extraction of Cd^{II} from spent electrolyte solution generated in Ni-Cd battery manufacturing²⁹. On the otherhand, Agh *et al.* studied the recovery and recycling of cadmium and nickel from the spent batteries³⁰.

In the present paper neutral extractant Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 has been applied for the extraction of cadmium from the spent of Ni-Cd battery. Rechargeable Panasonic

Ni-Cd battery manufactured by Matsushita Electric Industrial Co. Ltd., Japan was taken for analyses. The anode and the cathode paste was leached with concentrated hydrochloric acid, followed by removal of the graphite, iron and cobalt impurities by filtration, oxidation with NaOCl, followed by precipitation with NaOH. The real sample was found to contain $Cd^{II} = 15$ mg/ml and $Ni^{II} = 20$ mg/ml by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS).

The aliquot containing 50 μ g was taken, its acidity was adjusted to the required molarity (4.0 M/6.0 M HCl) and then it is equilibrated with equal volume of 0.3 M Cyanex-923/Cyanex-925 in toluene during which only Cd^{II} was extracted in the organic phase while Ni^{II} remained unextracted in the aqueous solution. The Cd^{II} was then stripped with 3.0 M $HClO_4$ and 2.0 M $HClO_4$ solution from the metal loaded organic phase of Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 respectively. The experimental results are in good agreement with theoretical values.

Conclusion :

- (i) The results obtained show that commercially available neutral phosphine oxide Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 in toluene can be used effectively for quantitative extraction of Cd^{II} from chloride media in the range 4.0–7.0 and 6.0–7.0 respectively.
- (ii) Incomplete extraction was observed in case of methyl isobutyl ketone (54%), Cyanex-302 from 0.1 M H_2SO_4/HCl (70% and 54%), diethyldithio carbamate¹⁵ (76%) and 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxyl-5'-sulformazylbenzene¹⁶. However, quantitative extraction was observed with both the extractants, Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925.
- (iii) Salting out agent which enhances the extraction was not required during the extraction of Cd^{II} with Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 compared to benzoyltrifluoroacetone and 2-thenoyltrifluoroacetone³¹ where addition of tetrabutyl ammonium ions increases the extraction of Cd^{II} .
- (iv) Di-(2-ethylhexyl)-dithiophosphoric acid (D2EHDTPA)⁹ quantitatively extracted Cd^{II} in toluene but its stripping was very difficult such problem was not found with both the extractants.
- (v) The proposed methods can be successfully applied for the recovery of Cd^{II} from the spent Ni-Cd battery.

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References

1. S. Kenji, A. Yoshfumi and N. Toshio, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **207**, 367.
2. A. M. Sastre, N. Miralles and E. Figuerola, *Solvent Extr. Ion Exch.*, 1990, **8**, 597.
3. K. Teofil and W. Janusz, *Pol. J. Appl. Chem.*, 1995, **39**, 203.
4. M. Yoshitaka and S. Yasuhito, *Solvent Extr. Res. Dev. Jpn.*, 1995, **2**, 53.
5. A. K. Nayak, P. K. Mishra, C. R. Panda and V. Chakravorty, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 1995, **2**, 111.
6. J. S. Presto and A. C. du Preez, *Solvent Extr. Ion Exch.*, 1994, **12**, 667.
7. B. A. Diantouba, I. Guiguemde, A. Tayeb, G. J. Goetz-Grandmont and J. P. Brunette, *Solvent Extr. Ion Exch.*, 1994, **12**, 325.
8. M. Maria, M. Nuria, S. Ana Maria and H. Concepcion, *Hydrometallurgy*, 1993, **33**, 95.
9. L. Lizhu, D. Zhang, X. Huiqin and K. Jiajun, *Chin. J. Chem. Engg.*, 1999, **7**, 132.
10. Z. R. Turel and M. M. David, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1999, **38**, 98.
11. W. A. Rickelton, *Solvent Extr. Ion Exch.*, 1999, **17**, 1507.
12. J. M. Singh and S. N. Tandon, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 897.
13. D. Hayati and R. W. Cattrall, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 779.
14. M. L. P. Reddy, S. Sujatha, T. R. Ramamohan, T. Prasada Rao, C. S. P. Iyer and A. R. Damodaran, *Radiochim. Acta*, 1995, **69**, 201.
15. O. Konard and L. Barbara, *Zesz. Nauk Politech. Slask. Chem.*, 1993, **1145**, 197.
16. L. Qiuyue, H. Guoliang, C. Chaowei, W. Kun and L. Weiqi, *Fenxi Huaxue*, 2000, **28**, 706.
17. L. Lizhu, Z. Dali, X. Huiqin and K. Jiajun, *Huagong Yejin*, 1999, **20**, 86.
18. S. Tatsuya, M. T. K. Dung and N. Junji, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1994, **67**, 432.
19. W. Bin, W. Kaiyi and Z. Xianglin, *Wuji Huaxue Xuebao*, 1991, **7**, 262.
20. L. Xin-Fang, D. Ding-Sheng, M. Ming and W. Shu-Mei, *Wuji Huaxue Xuebao*, 2003, **19**, 1295.
21. C. Bing-Yi, J. Hui-Xai, L. Quan-Min and L. Guo-Guang, *Yingyong Huaxue*, 2004, **21**, 54.
22. B. D. Jamel, D. Zoubir and T. Abdelkader, *Turkish J. Chem.*, 2001, **25**, 381.
23. R. L. Hinojosa, M. I. Saucedo, M. R. Navarro, V. J. Revilla, R. M. Avila and E. Guibal, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2001, **40**, 1422.
24. M. Gonzalez, S. Imelda, N. Ricardo, A. Mario and G. Eric, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2001, **40**, 6004.
25. A. I. Vogel, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longman, London, 1975, 495.

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26. M. Otomo, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1964, **37**, 504.
27. T. Sato and T. Nakamura, *Hydrometallurgy*, 1980, **6**, 3.
28. U. S. Bureau of Mines, "Minerals Industry Surveys, Cadmium", U.S. Department of the Interior, Washington, D.C., 1989 and 1990.
29. Y. K. P. Sze and J. K. S. Lam, *Environ. Technol.*, 1999, **20**, 943.
30. A. Jonoés, H. Tamas, M. Janos, K. Sandor, S. Ildiko and V. Karoly, *Hug. Teljes HU 55, 451 (Cl. C22B3/00)*, 28 May 1991, *Appl.* 89/6, **189**, 27 Nov, 13.
31. S. Tatsuya, M. T. K. Dung and N. Junji, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1994, **62**, 432.